

Figured Magic Squares of Orders 18 and 20 Using Bordered Magic Rectangles: A Systematic Procedure

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Abstract

Recently, author constructed even order magic squares from orders 6 to 20 with different styles and models, for examples the order 20 is with 1616 magic squares, order 18 with 810 magic squares, etc. These can be seen at [31, 32, 33, 33, 34, 35, 36]. The aim is to proceed for the further orders of magic squares. In this work there are few examples of magic squares given as figures of orders 18 and 20. A systematic procedure to construct these magic squares is given. It is based on the magic squares and bordered magic rectangles (BMR) of orders 4, 6, 8 etc forming external borders. Then the internal borders are filled with previous known magic squares. The presentations is in figures instead of numbers. The readers can find replies in numbers from references given above. For the orders multiples of 4, we can always write magic squares with equal sums blocks of magic squares of order 4. This procedure is very helpful for the orders of type $2p$, where p is a prime number, for examples, 14, 22, 26, 34, 38, etc. For the orders like 18, 30, etc. we can make good external blocks with order 4, and for orders like 16, 20, 28, 32, etc. we can make good external borders of order 6, and so on.

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Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Magic Squares of Order 18	4
2.1	Bordered and Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 18	4
2.2	Cornered Magic Squares of Order 4	8
2.3	Closed Border of Order 4	14
2.4	Closed Border of Order 6	20
2.5	Blocks of Order 8 and 10	23
2.6	Extra Examples	26
3	Magic Squares of Order 20	34
3.1	Bordered and Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 20	34
3.2	Magic Squares of Order 20 With BMR	38
3.3	Cornered Magic Squares of Order 4	42
3.4	Closed Border of Order 4	51
3.5	Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6	60
3.6	Closed Border of Order 6	64
3.7	Magic Squares of Order 10	68
3.8	Two Consecutive BMR	76
4	Appendix	79
5	Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers	81

1 Introduction

The magic sums of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3. \quad (1)$$

Recently, the author [31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36] constructed magic squares of even orders from 6 to 20 using **bordered magic rectangles**. This construction is based on two aspects:

- (i) Using **magic rectangles** or **bordered magic rectangles**.
- (ii) Using algebraic formula like $(\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b})^2, \mathbf{a} \neq \mathbf{b}$.

For the above magic squares no construction procedure is explained. The aim is to proceed further orders of magic squares. In this work, a systematic procedure to construct these magic squares is given. It is based on the magic squares and bordered magic rectangles (BMR) of orders 4, 6, 8 etc forming external borders. Then the internal borders are filled with previous known magic squares. For the orders multiples of 4, we can always write magic squares with equal sums blocks of magic squares of order 4. This procedure is very helpful for the orders of type $2\mathbf{p}$, where \mathbf{p} is a prime number, for examples, 14, 22, 26, 34, 38, etc. For the orders like 18, 30, etc., we can make good external blocks with order 4, and for orders like 16, 20, 28, 32, etc. we can make good external borders of order 6, and so on. There is no explanations for the orders 6, 8, 10 and 12. The real construction starts from the order 14.

The whole the work is done manually, without use of any programming language, except for the constructions of small blocks of **bordered magic rectangles**. This construction is based on the software due to H. While. Later, these BRM's are readopted according to distribution of each magic square. The distribution of magic squares or bordered magic rectangles is based on **half-sequential** numbers. By **half-sequential** numbers we understand that the total numbers

in each case are divided in two equal parts. First part is one sequence and second part is another sequence. Due to **half-sequential** numbers, it is not possible to construct all orders **bordered magic rectangles**. In Appendix 4, there are tables showing the existence of these **bordered magic rectangles** for **half-sequential**. For simplicity, we shall write **BMR** as **bordered magic rectangle**.

2 Magic Squares of Order 18

This section brings in figures (without numbers) magic squares of order 18. In some case its construction is explained. For details refer author's work [34].

2.1 Bordered and Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 18

Below are four magic squares of order 18 already known in the literature.

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2 Inder J. Taneja <https://inderjtaneja.com/> <https://numbers-magic.com/>

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2.2 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 4

Let's consider an external border of where there are 4 magic squares of order 4 at the corners. In middle, let's put a bordered magic rectangles of order 4×10 . In the middle we are left with block of order 10. Writing middle block of order 10 in different ways, below are few examples of magic squares of order 18.

2.3 Closed Border of Order 4

Let's consider 4 equal sums BMR of order 4×14 . then we left with internal block of order 10. Writing middle block of order 10 in different ways, below are few examples of magic squares of order 18.

2.4 Closed Border of Order 6

According to Fig 2, subsection of order 6, we don't require to write cornered magic squares of order 6. Let's write four equal sum four blocks of order 6×12 and putting them as external closed border of order 6. We are left internal border of order 6. Below are few examples:

2.5 Blocks of Order 8 and 10

Below are three examples based on the blocks of orders 8 and 10.

2.6 Extra Examples

Below are few examples of mixed types magic squares of order 18.

3 Magic Squares of Order 20

This section brings in figures (without numbers) magic squares of order 20. In some case its construction is explained. For details refer author's work [35].

3.1 Bordered and Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 20

Below are four magic squares of order 20 already known in the literature.

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2 Inder J. Taneja <https://inderjtaneja.com/> <https://numbers-magic.com/>

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3.2 Magic Squares of Order 20 With BMR

Below are four magic squares of order 20 made with BMR. In each case the construction is individual.

3.3 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 4

According to Fig.1 given in subsection 3.1, we don't require cornered magic squares of order 4. We are writing here as an extra option. Let's consider an external border, where there are 4 magic squares of order 4 at the corners. In middle, let's put two BMR of order 4×6 . In the

middle we are left with block of order 12. Writing middle block of order 12 in different ways, below are few examples of magic squares of order 20.

3.4 Closed Border of Order 4

Let's consider 4 equal sums BMR of order 4×10 and of order 4×6 . then we left with internal block of order 12. Writing middle block of order 12 in different ways, below are few examples of magic squares of order 20.

3.5 Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6

Let's consider 4 magic squares of order 6 and 4 BMR of order 6×8 . This gives us a external border of order 6. We are left with inner block of order 8. Writing middle block of order 8 in different ways, below are few examples of magic squares of order 20.

3.6 Closed Border of Order 6

Let's consider 2 BMR of order 6×20 and two of order 6×8 . This gives us a external border of order 6. We are left with inner block of order 8. Writing middle block of order 8 in different ways, below are few examples of magic squares of order 20.

3.7 Magic Squares of Order 10

Let's consider 4 equal sums magic squares of order 10. This gives different type of magic squares of order 20. See below:

3.8 Two Consecutive BMR

The following magic squares are constructed based on two consecutive BMR of orders 8×10 and 10×12

4 Appendix

Below are tables giving the existence of **bordered magic rectangles** for **half-sequential** numbers.

Order of Magic Square	Bordered Magic Rectangles
6	4×6
8	6×8
10	$4 \times 10, 8 \times 10$
12	$6 \times 12, 10 \times 12$
14	$4 \times 14, 8 \times 14, 12 \times 14$
16	$6 \times 16, 10 \times 16, 14 \times 16$
18	$4 \times 18, 8 \times 18, 12 \times 18$
20	$6 \times 20, 10 \times 20, 14 \times 20, 18 \times 20$
22	$4 \times 22, 8 \times 22, 12 \times 22,$ $16 \times 22, 20 \times 22$
24	$6 \times 24, 10 \times 24, 14 \times 24,$ $18 \times 24, 22 \times 24$
26	$4 \times 26, 8 \times 26, 12 \times 26,$ $16 \times 26, 20 \times 26, 24 \times 26$
28	$6 \times 28, 10 \times 28, 14 \times 28,$ $18 \times 28, 22 \times 28, 26 \times 28$
30	$4 \times 30, 8 \times 30, 12 \times 30, 16 \times 30,$ $20 \times 30, 24 \times 30, 28 \times 30$
32	$6 \times 32, 10 \times 32, 14 \times 32, 18 \times 32,$ $22 \times 32, 26 \times 32, 30 \times 32$
34	$4 \times 34, 8 \times 34, 12 \times 34, 16 \times 34,$ $20 \times 34, 24 \times 34, 28 \times 34, 32 \times 34$

Order of Magic Square	Bordered Magic Rectangles
36	$6 \times 36, 10 \times 36, 14 \times 36, 18 \times 36,$ $22 \times 36, 26 \times 36, 30 \times 36, 34 \times 36$
38	$4 \times 38, 8 \times 38, 12 \times 38, 16 \times 38, 20 \times 38,$ $24 \times 38, 28 \times 38, 32 \times 38, 36 \times 38$
40	$6 \times 40, 10 \times 40, 14 \times 40, 18 \times 40, 22 \times 40,$ $26 \times 40, 30 \times 40, 34 \times 40, 38 \times 40$
42	$4 \times 42, 8 \times 42, 12 \times 42, 16 \times 42, 20 \times 42,$ $24 \times 42, 28 \times 42, 32 \times 42, 36 \times 42, 40 \times 42$
44	$6 \times 44, 10 \times 44, 14 \times 44, 18 \times 44, 22 \times 44, 26 \times 44,$ $30 \times 44, 34 \times 44, 38 \times 44, 42 \times 44$
46	$4 \times 46, 8 \times 46, 12 \times 46, 16 \times 46, 20 \times 46, 24 \times 46,$ $28 \times 46, 32 \times 46, 36 \times 46, 40 \times 46, 44 \times 46$
48	$6 \times 48, 10 \times 48, 14 \times 48, 18 \times 48, 22 \times 48, 26 \times 48,$ $30 \times 48, 34 \times 48, 38 \times 48, 42 \times 48, 46 \times 48$
50	$4 \times 50, 8 \times 50, 12 \times 50, 16 \times 50, 20 \times 50, 24 \times 50,$ $28 \times 50, 32 \times 50, 36 \times 50, 40 \times 50, 44 \times 50, 48 \times 50$

5 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- Inder J. Taneja, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- Inder J. Taneja, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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